

1 **Kinetically programmed myosin activation and repression during differentiation to the**
2 **trophoectoderm in human embryonic stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of a
9 kinetically patterned myosin activation and repression program during differentiation to the trophoectoderm
10 in human embryonic stem cells with functions in lineage commitment.

11 Citations

12 1. Chen, G., Hou, Z., Gulbranson, D.R. and Thomson, J.A., 2010. Actin-myosin contractility is
13 responsible for the reduced viability of dissociated human embryonic stem cells. Cell stem cell, 7(2),
14 pp.240-248.